

Mapping OER And The Open Education Milestone In Nigeria

by

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ABOUT

This report stems from the end result of a course in the pilot year of [the Leadership in Open Education Master's program](#) of the [University of Nova Gorica](#). The course, a Team Project is conducted by Prof. Dr. Tel Amiel; professor at the School of Education at the University of Brasilia where he coordinates the UNESCO Chair in Distance Education and Larry Cooperman, the former president of the Open Education Consortium and former Associate Dean for Open Education at the University of California, Irvine.

The purpose of the project is to take a panoramic view of the OER landscape in Nigeria and also to contribute to [the OER World Map](#), an online catalogue of OER initiatives across the globe, followed by a series of interview with key personnel in the OE sphere anchored alongside my colleague Ana Fabjan from Slovenia.

I am Adéşínà Ghani Ayèni otherwise known as Ọmọ Yoòbá, a multimedia journalist, digital right activist, anthropologist and OER developer with interest in creation of open content in the Yoruba language of West Africa. I am a professional translator, Yorùbá Lingua Manager for Global Voices, and the founder of Yobamoodua Cultural Heritage, a Language Service Provider and Yorùbá information services organization.

1 MAPPING OPEN EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

1.1 Education in Nigeria (an overview)

Nigeria, a country located in West Africa with a population of 211 million people (Worldometer), a Land Area of 910,770km², and officially called the Federal Republic of Nigeria is made up of 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory. The country has over five hundred ethnic groups, and over 525 native languages. It has a Growth Rate of 2.60%, a 21,087 Birth per Day and 6,507 Deaths per Day. The average Nigerian citizen is relatively young, 18.4 years of age as the median age of both males and females (World Population Review).

Figure 1- Population of Nigeria between the year 1950 - 2020 (worldpopulationreview.com)

Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba are the three most spoken languages in Nigeria after English which is the official language. Though English is the major language of instruction in Education, the native languages that is Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba are used in the first 3 years of elementary school and in language subjects at regional levels. A 2018 literacy report by [Statista](https://www.statista.com) (Simona Varrella, 2020) shows that males are more literate with a total of 86.4% in the urban area, 59.5% in the rural area; while 74% of the female population in the urban and 35.4% in the rural area are considered literates.

Education is overseen by Nigerian Ministry of Education while the Nigerian University Commission is in charge of all activities of higher education. The education system is divided into Kindergarten, Primary education, Secondary education, and Tertiary education. Compulsory education in Nigeria is in a span of 9 years (grades 1-9) usually between the ages of 6 and 15. However, early education is not compulsory and only 40 percent of the population enroll their child in crèches, nurseries or kindergartens.

Figure 2- Nigeria Education System (wenr.wes.org)

In 1973, the 6-3-3-4 education system was introduced; 6 years in elementary school, 3 years junior secondary, 3 years senior secondary school and 4 years in higher education. Primary education begins at around age 5/6 for most Nigerians to complete education around age 11/12 as the case may be, whereas the learner moves to the first three years of secondary school.

According to [UNICEF](http://www.unicef.org) (Esiebo, 2013) about 10.5 million children are not in school even though primary education is officially free and compulsory. The gross enrollment rate in elementary schools in Nigeria is 68.3%, of which 22.4 million children are enrolled in public elementary schools.

The six years of primary school is added to the 3 years in junior secondary school to make up the 9 years compulsory education. While the student may decide to move on to the next three years of secondary education (senior education) and afterwards proceed to tertiary institution or vocational training. It is requisite to state that the six years spent in the primary and six years secondary school (JSS1 to SSS3) is equivalent to 12th Grade.

According to a 2020 report published by Statista (Simona Varrella, 2020), the gross enrollment rate in lower secondary school (Junior Secondary School) is 54.4% (6.8 million students) while 68.6% is the gross enrollment rate in upper secondary school with 80% males completing the upper secondary school compared to 59% of the female population.

There are 170 universities in Nigeria; 43 being Federal universities; 48 State universities; 79 private universities and 211 polytechnics; 28 Federal polytechnics; 43 state polytechnics; 51 private polytechnics; 22 federal colleges of education; 47 state colleges of education; 20 private colleges of education. In 2017, there was over 960,417 male and 750,717 female undergraduate students, 139,504 male and 83,925 postgraduate students in Nigerian universities ([statista 2020](#)).

Data from between 2012 and 2018 shows that the expenditure on education fluctuates in Nigeria, with 2014 been the highest (10.54%), 2015 (10.28%), 2013 (10.15%), 2012 (9.86%), 2016 (7.92%), 2017 and 2018 (7.4%), which amount to 653 billion naira.

Figure 3 - Education Expenditure in Nigeria between 2012 and 2018 ([statista.com](#))

1.2 Brief history of OE in Nigeria

Having looked at the statistics, let us examine the [historical developments of OE in Nigeria](#). Unlike the Global North where distance education has gained strong ground in the education industry, it is still in the early stage in the Global South yet to have a footing in the Nigerian education system with a number of challenges. However, the government has established some institutions to facilitate the growth of distance learning, the likes of National Teachers Institute (NTI) for the training of teachers, the [National Open University of Nigeria \(NOUN\)](#) for those who could not afford to leave their job to attend full time conventional education and many others.

Open and Distance Learning (ODL) was introduced to the university education system in 1983 through the NOUN, though it was suspended in 1985 by the military government and it became functional in 2001. Hence NOUN is the first full-fledged university that operates in an exclusive ODL mode of education. ODL practice in Nigeria comes in various forms; correspondence study education, distance learning (Sandwich programmes), Part-Time Teacher Training Programme (PTTP), Open University, weekend programmes, adult literacy education programmes, National Teachers Institute (NTI) and e-learning. However in June 2020, the National Universities Commission (NUC) approved 11 more universities to operate a dual-mode learning (Desert Herald, 2020); both conventional

learning and Open Distance Learning (ODL) and the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) which is the only Nigerian university that operates a ‘uni-mode learning system’ makes the [ODL institutions in Nigeria 12](#) in number.

2 OER MAPPING RESEARCH

2.1 About the OER World Map site

The OER World Map is an online open access database for the dissemination of OER initiatives across the globe funded by The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation. With the OER World Map finding Open Education Resources initiatives in various regions of the world is easy and it is growing day-by-day in quantity with resources ranging from projects, policies, higher institutions of learning, publications, libraries, and so on.

2.2 Data collection

Although there are not so much open education resources in Nigeria aside from the few ones owned by institutions of higher education, few independent projects and government agencies, however, a thorough analysis of the OER World Map shows that there are only a few resources on the map; 20 persons, 3 services, 2 organizations, 2 publications, 1 story and 1 event.

Figure 4 – OER on the OER World Map before my research (image created by me)

Data for the project were collated via online search queries and suggestions from colleagues. At first, I expected easy modification of the data already on the map, but this was not the case, a user is not allowed to edit other entries made by other users, therefore I only added 28 data collated by myself while I could not modify those added by other persons. After adding the data from my research, Nigeria is now heavily represented on the map with 53 resources. I made 28 entries; 13 organizations (higher institutions of learning); 1 service; 1 person; 1 project; 12 publications.

Figure 5 – OER on the OER World Map after my research (Screen print of the OER World Map)

Below is a table showing my entries on the OER World Map.

	ORGANIZATIONS (HIGHER INSTITUTIONS OF LEARNING)
1	
Resource	University of Port Harcourt (UNIPORT)
Description	The University of Port Harcourt is located in the city of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. UNIPORT was established in 1975 as University College, Port Harcourt and it became a University in 1977. In the year 2015, UNIPORT was ranked the sixth in Africa and the first in Nigeria by Times Higher Education (THE).
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:f154d523-a18e-42f7-87a4-bde95dee4266
2	
Resource	University of Jos (UNIJOS)
Description	The University of Jos (UNIJOS) located in Plateau State started as a campus of the University of Ibadan in 1971, and became a full higher institution in 1975. The institution's library and repository are open to the public.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:e6946427-3c6d-4f8d-a405-f69c102007a2
3	
Resource	University of Abuja
Description	The University of Abuja was established under Decree No. 110 of 1992 as a dual-mode university with the mandate to run conventional and distance learning programmes on January 1, 1988. UNIABUJA OER repository archived over 559,950 open educational resources for educators.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:08ba422a-d47b-4fd0-b6ef-85205ab810f3
4	
Resource	University of Maiduguri (UNIMAID)

Description	The University of Maiduguri (UNIMAID) is one of the Federal Government owned higher institution in Nigeria created in 1975. UNIMAID is located in Maiduguri, Borno State.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:0a10bbeb-1ffe-4db1-8d11-13110233c6ad
5	
Resource	Ambrose Alli University (AAU)
Description	The Ambrose Alli University (AAU) was established in 1981 by Prof. Ambrose Folorunsho Alli. To meet modern digital standards, the state-owned higher institution made some educational material like courseware, conference papers, projects, books, videos and other resources available for free download.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:e6946427-3c6d-4f8d-a405-f69c102007a2
6	
Resource	Obafemi Awolowo University
Description	Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife is one of three Universities established in Nigeria between 1961 and 1962. The University website has some free institutional research journals, inaugural lectures, theses and dissertations, speeches & special lectures for scholarly works.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:bfcabd09-6d20-4f2b-abcf-b2170162ea81
7	
Resource	Babcock University
Description	Babcock University which began as Adventist College of West Africa (ACWA) in 1959. To attain national recognition for its programmes, ACWA obtained a local affiliation with University of Ibadan, under the name “Babcock College”. In 1999, the Federal Government of Nigeria included Babcock University as one of the first three private universities in the country.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:a79192f1-a4f6-4098-b489-6a256cfdecfb
8	
Resource	The University of Lagos (UNILAG)
Description	The University of Lagos (UNILAG) was founded in 1962. Unilag has three campuses in Yaba and Surulere, as well as a Distance Learning Institute (DLI). The University of Lagos Digital Repository for research and teaching materials created by the University Library provides open and permanent access to University of Lagos scholarship thereby ensuring its wide dissemination and increased visibility online.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:e6946427-3c6d-4f8d-a405-f69c102007a2
9	
Resource	Coal City University (CCU)
Description	Coal City University is ranked 76 in Nigeria and 10209 in the world. Coal City University is a private higher-education institution established in 2016 and located in Enugu State, Nigeria. The Coal City University’s (CCU) Open Educational Resources (OER) though still growing, has over 177 free and open educational resources which includes books, presentations, journal, report, thesis & dissertations, lecture notes, lecture videos, courseware and other OER.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:e6946427-3c6d-4f8d-a405-f69c102007a2
10	
Resource	University of Nigeria Nsukka (UNN)
Description	The University of Nigeria Nsukka, whose motto is “to restore the dignity of man” is a federal university situated in Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria. Popularly referred to as UNN, the institution was founded in 1955 by the late Nnamdi Azikiwe and officially opened on the 7th of October 1960. UNN has three campuses in Enugu State and one campus in Abia State.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:b37cb16b-41c0-478b-aa61-d0c128b84d68

11	
Resource	National University Commission (NUC)
Description	The National University Commission (NUC) is a parastatal under the Federal Ministry of Education (FME) established in 1962 as an advisory agency in the Cabinet Office. As a coordinating body, the Commission ensures it discharges its responsibilities by recruiting adequate and relevant man power and appeals to the university for their sustained support and understanding.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:8b1bfabc-0010-4cac-8be1-741586fb9180
12	
Resource	Nnamdi Azikiwe University (UNIZIK)
Description	Nnamdi Azikiwe University (UNIZIK) located in Awka, Anambra State of Nigeria came into being in the year 1991 and was taken over by the Federal Government by Decree No. 34 of July 15, 1992. The name of the university is an eponymous of Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe. NAU Open Educational Resources (OER) is a repository of educational materials with textbooks, curricula, syllabi, lecture notes, lecture videos, assignments, test, projects, audio-visuals, etc.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:09e32852-01df-41e1-9f15-271a044ef7c3
13	
Resource	Yorùbá-Scipedia
Description	In a bid to bridge the digital divide, language marginalization and make the internet more inclusive, the wiki Yoruba-Scipedia project developed by Dr. Julius Fákiledé to make available contents in the Yorùbá language of West Africa. The encyclopedia boasts of resources in Biology, Physics, Geography and more for educators of science and technology.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:ac6dcad0-2649-41ef-b90b-422c2ba60688

PUBLICATIONS	
1	
Resource	GRID3 NIGERIA
Description	Grid3 Nigeria; Geo-Referenced Infrastructure and Demographic Data for Development Programme launched in 2018, has 1247 open datasets from 37 states and 12 sectors viz agriculture, commerce, education, energy, health and so on.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:f154d523-a18e-42f7-87a4-bde95dee4266
2	
Resource	HUMANITARIAN DATA EXCHANGE
Description	The Humanitarian Data Exchange is a repository created to find, share and use humanitarian data all in one place. There are over 18,984 datasets from 1,435 sources and anyone can contribute by adding humanitarian data to the databank.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:32da7669-bda3-43a0-90b7-e75e7c71f72f
3	
Resource	OPEN DATA PORTAL (ODP)
Description	Open Data Portal (ODP) is an initiative by the Ministry of Communications and Digital Economy in line with its E-Governance strategy and masterplan for Nigeria. The aim of the platform is to promote accountability, transparency and inclusiveness by releasing government data through a dedicated repository.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:e07bc34e-b588-479d-8d6e-ebe1f3ac0be1
4	
Resource	Nigeria Open Contracting Portal (NOCOPO)

Description	Nigeria Open Contracting Portal (NOCOPO) is to open up public procurement in Nigeria through increased disclosure of procurement information to all stakeholders. The NOCOPO portal is a fulfilment of Commitment 2 of the Nigeria National Action Plan of the Open Government Partnership.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:a8af4616-beb9-480a-aa93-e1ca74bed7e3
5	
Resource	Open Treasury
Description	Open Treasury is a directory of open data on the Nigerian treasury both for the Federal and State Government. The directory has treasury statement, payment reports, budget performance report and even COVID-19 reports.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:d7579f0a-67dc-4aae-acb6-2e00d6539813
6	
Resource	Nigerian Bureau of Statistics
Description	The Nigerian Bureau of Statistics is the apex statistical agency for the three tiers of government in Nigeria. Its website provides open data on statistics with various reports on entertainment, banking sector, food price, state revenue, etc. The site is also linked back to other government open sites and documents.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:cb9dd538-613c-4c9e-84a6-3284c8872493
7	
Resource	Nigeria Data Portal
Description	Nigeria Data Portal is enriched with open government data ranging from state-to-state data, census data, employment and unemployment rate data, and many more.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:2fb6dba8-499d-4af2-921c-183f1871ab90
8	
Resource	Open Government Partnership
Description	Open Government Partnership works with both national and local government agencies as well as civil society organizations across the world to enhance transparency, accountability and public participation in government based on a submitted action plan. These action plans are made open to the public for research purposes.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:9ef4d879-f438-4496-ac05-0a179c743a8a
9	
Resource	Zaccheus Onumba Dibiaezue Memorial Libraries
Description	Zaccheus Onumba Dibiaezue Memorial Libraries has a large and varied collection of eBooks that are easily downloaded in epub, kindle formats or read online. There are over 59554 eBooks from the architecture, business and management, computing, history, medicine and other categories on the e-Library.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:fa31e7c0-4f49-428d-a156-0464d76c500f
10	
Resource	LESSONPLAN
Description	Lessonplan is an educational platform for Primary, Secondary schools' students and teachers. The platform has scheme of work, lesson notes, lesson plans and examination questions.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:db0f0dcf-08ed-44f1-8eea-28b46ef68c9d
11	
Resource	Yorùbá-Scipedia
Description	In a bid to bridge the digital divide, language marginalization and make the internet more inclusive, the wiki Yoruba-Scipedia project developed by Dr. Julius Fákilèdé to make available contents in the Yorùbá language of West Africa. The encyclopedia boasts of

	resources in Biology, Physics, Geography and more for educators of science and technology.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:e6946427-3c6d-4f8d-a405-f69c102007a2
12	
Resource	YOBAMOODUA CULTURAL HERITAGE (YMCH)
Description	No matter who you are, or what you do, be you a student, developer or teacher, Yobamoodua.org is your one stop Yorùbá language, cultural values and traditions website; a database for general information about the Yorùbá cultural heritage. YMCH conduct research, organizes language classes, host translation sprint event whereby linguistics, students, journalists and other professionals in the education and tech industry converged to create new or modify old terms; words; nomenclature whether in biology, history and what have you from all works of life.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:576bea59-3b4a-4a6d-af17-1b01857c885f

	SERVICE
1	
Resource	Digital Library Nigeria
Description	The digital library of the British Council in Nigeria is a databank of learning resources from eBooks, magazines, newspaper, comics, graphic novels, audio books, movies and documentaries. To access the resources, users are to register online to read, borrow and learn with the Digital Library.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:abe2aed7-6822-4044-8c5d-2a6524a7d11d
	PERSON
1	
Resource	Adesina Ayeni
Description	A journalist with keen interest in digital inclusion, bridging the digital divide and marginalization of the African languages in general; the Yorùbá language in particular. In the past 10 years, he has translated a wide range of digital resources as well as worked with international agencies viz Localiation Lab, Engine Room, and Creative Commons to localize OER to Yorùbá language. Adésínà Ayeni (Ọmọ Yoòbá) is the Yorùbá Lingua Manager, Global Voices.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:ae49b1d1-3b1d-4c2b-8c0a-562920b643ef
	PROJECT
1	
Resource	OYSGEDU
Description	The Oyo State Government, under the Oyo State Ministry of Education, Science and Technology designed a digital platform to foster an ICT-driven education.
Link to map	https://oerworldmap.org/resource/urn:uuid:b1177cfa-04a4-4735-ab55-6a447f58695e

3 INTERVIEW

3.1 The interview process

As part of the Team Project, an exposé of the Open Education landscape in Nigeria from two knowledgeable persons in the field of OE was carried out. The investigation employed the interviewee-interviewer approach, and the two resource persons selected were Prof. Jane-Frances Obiageli Agbu and Dr. Julius Káyodé Fákilèdé.

Using a questionnaire of specific questions to each interviewee, the interview was conducted together with my project team member, Ana Fabjan on the Zoom platform. They were recorded, transcribed and analyzed. A draft copy was sent to the interviewees for approval before the final report. The interview questions centers around the project the interviewee is undertaken, the milestones of OER in Nigeria, the merits and challenges of OER in Nigeria, the sustainability of the OER project, and collaboration with other stakeholders.

3.2 Prof. Jane-Frances Obiageli Agbu - NOUN

The first interviewee was Prof. Jane-Frances Obiageli Agbu, professor of clinical psychology, an ICDE Chair in Open Educational Resources, a laureate of 2016 Open Leadership Institute of Creative Commons and currently Associate Professor of Clinical Psychology of the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN). She strongly advocates the opening-up of knowledge for common good, a humanistic stance that upholds access, education equity and equality for all in Nigeria. Jane-Frances has been in the field of Open Education since 2006. She is an expert in open education with over 15 years' experience in advising faculty, institutions and government in open education and more recently, Open Educational Resources (OER). Jane-Frances' zeal paved the way for her to stimulate the embrace of OER by her Institution NOUN in 2014, and this led to massive capacity building and sensitization. Her tenacity at championing OER in NOUN won her the award of excellence in open education for her institution by [Open Education Consortium \(OEC\)](#) in 2016. In furtherance of the fulfilment of her passion, and with the supervision of Commonwealth of Learning and the National Universities Commission (NUC), Nigeria, Jane-Frances was instrumental in the drafting of an OER policy for higher education in Nigeria presented to the heads of Higher Institutions in Nigeria in September 2017. The draft Policy was afterward approved by the Federal Government of Nigeria, with a National Steering Committee put in motion to oversee its implementation and adoption, of which Jane-Frances is a member.

3.3 Dr. Julius Káyodé Fákilèdé – Yoruba-scipedia

Next interview was with Dr. Julius Káyodé Fákilèdé, trustee of the Association of Educators of Science and Technology in the Yorùbá language, and a chemist by profession. He has been in the chemistry field and the science generally for about close to four or five decades. He worked as a lecturer in the Federal University of Technology Akure, Nigeria, taught in the King University and Rodgers University in the United States. He has been working on the progress of education for more than 30 years, as an educator, Dr. Julius Káyodé Fákilèdé has published many books including a modern Yorùbá dictionary.

As an industrial chemist his interest is to make sure that much of the knowledge that abound in the sciences are made available to Nigerians and Africans in the indigenous languages, so that the continent can progress rapidly in that area because many a times the way education is inoculated in

Africa does not make easy for progress, this is what led him to the creation of [Yoruba-scipedia](#) project which is a result of a collaborative effort with interested persons and like minds.

4 RESEARCH ANALYSIS

A critical look at the data collated from the interview and findings while gathering the entries for the OER World Map points to the fact that Open Education is still at the teething level in Nigeria, and the OER World Map attest to this fact with little OER activities present. Much of the resources gathered from the research are by HE institutions, open data from government agencies and a few individual projects. Although some of the data collected claim to be free and open for reuse, they did not utilize the [Creative Commons Licenses](#) on the resources and this pose a concern for me while working on the map.

Working in the field of open education was by sheer chance for Prof. Jane-Frances Obiageli Agbu, because she worked in the conventional system of education with no ICT skills or background in open education. But things changed when she stumbled on NOUN in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. She approached the NOUN, she got the job and became a director, and she coordinates the study centers which boast of more than 7,000 students.

According to Prof. Agbu, the beginning was rough for her and her institution as they grappled with the misconception of the open philosophy. The conventional universities were against the open system and clamoured for the sanction of NOUN for impacting ‘half-baked knowledge’; they believe it is impossible to teach via internet or to use just technology; the phone to go to the normal classroom without the one-to-one; teacher in front of the student approach. The open system practice of NOUN that gives many students admission that would not get in the old system, which angers the conventional institutions. Going forward, there were lots of negative perceptions, and media reportage till it got to a point where going to work was not really enthusiastic even some of her colleagues at work could not come to accept the concept of open education where a student learn without seeing the teacher face-to-face. At a time, her professor at UNILAG who was supposed to give her a reference letter for an OE opportunity refused to do so, claiming she was only going to waste her years of training in an Open University system.

With OE, education is taken to more people, and in a highly populated country like Nigeria. On a yearly basis, over 1.8/1.4 million students take the Joint Admission Matriculation Board (JAMB) examination, whereas the carrying capacity of the conventional universities both public and private is usually 400 intakes. This gap is what the National Open University of Nigeria fills by reaching the unreached, providing educational opportunities to people that do not even have chance of qualification. Some of the OE milestones in Nigeria are attributed to her institution, like the over hundred study centres and community study centres in remote areas across Nigeria.

Prisoners leave the [prisons with a PhD](#), immigration service and the association of road transport workers also benefit from the system. In the northern region women in purdah who do not leave their matrimonial homes are able to earn a degree through the open education system.

Other milestones are the numerous sensitizations, technical related training and collaboration with other institutions plus the countless workshops through the region training for Open & Distance Learning, a Common Wealth of Learning funded institute known as the Regional Training & Research Institute for Open & Distance Learning (*RETRIDAL*) domiciled in NOUN.

In all, the major milestone credited to her is the development of an OER policy for Higher Education in Nigeria coordinated by the Common Wealth of Learning in collaboration with the National Universities Commission (NUC). Relying on a template and guide by Sanjir Mitcha of [Common](#)

[Wealth of Learning](#), the draft was completed within two months. The draft policy was presented at a gathering of [stakeholders in 2017](#) attended by Nigerian university Vice Chancellors, ICT directors and others. Later that year, a presentation of the policy was delivered at the Ljubljana OER meeting and it was adopted afterwards by the National Council for Education. Though the draft has been endorsed by the Federal Ministry of Education and available online, it is currently in the final stage waiting for the last signature before it is distributed to universities in Nigeria.

Defining the concept of Open Education, Prof. Jane-Frances highlighted that OE is the philosophy of openness, the philosophy of access, inclusiveness, equity, and the opportunity for everybody to study at anytime, anywhere, and at any place. In addition, she opined that Open Education is about opening up knowledge, it's for common good, and that access is about open licenses.

Speaking of challenges, convincing her colleagues in the academic world about OE was the most tasking. Nonetheless she employed the use of gift items; tea cups, pens, food flasks and stickers sponsored by UNESCO to attract their attention whenever a workshop is staged.

Jane-Frances hinted that the effort to make knowledge open is actually more in people's minds, many stakeholders to some extent knows about it, but the reality of it has not been concretized as it has not been wholly implemented at all levels. The government should be in the fore, all school textbooks funded with tax payers' money by the Tertiary Education Fund (TETfund; the national funding organization that funds research) should be made available for public use free of charge with open license and not sold back to the people.

Last but not the least, Prof. Jane-Frances is of the opinion that both government and individuals need to look into localization of educational resources so that the non-English speaking community can have access to education in their native tongues.

Like Prof. Jane-Frances said, Dr. Julius Káyodé Fákilèdé also mentioned that the need for resources in native languages is of utmost priority in the development of the education system. While having the conversation with him, Dr. Julius stated that the idea of the encyclopaedia in the Yorùbá language emanated from previous teaching experiences and the idea of learning science in the native language at an early age. To set the ball rolling, a group of interested persons with a similar mindset, who understands the benefits that comes with learning science and tech in the mother tongue, known as the *Association of Educators of Science and Technology in Yorùbá language* (AESTYL) was inaugurated. Five years ago, a virtual Facebook education group run by the association was initiated and conversation around science subjects in the Yorùbá indigenous language took centre stage on the group. Around the same time collation of some of the research that have been studied and perfected in the past 20, 30, 40 and 50 years ago and has been written including the resources that have been discussed on the Facebook page culminated in the Yoruba-scipedia campaign.

The objective of the Yoruba-scipedia project is to collate all scientific materials that have been published in the Yorùbá language, to develop new resources through translation efforts and then put them all on the web for everybody to access it, a place where anyone can always go every day to learn something without having to go through the normal education process, without the need of passing an exam or go to college. The fact that OE allows the usage of open educational resources by the public helps Yoruba-scipedia in the attempt to make education open to everybody in a bilingual format.

He further said that the main objective of education is the propagation of information and that is why open educational resource gives the learner the opportunity to learn about something today to be continued at the learner's own pace. For him, Open Education Resources is a digital tool on a digital space where one is able to learn about anything and expand one's own horizon without being limited by the government or any other limitation that makes it difficult for people to learn.

Talking about the milestones of Open Education in Nigeria, Dr. Julius believes that Nigeria is developing slowly in terms of the adoption of the OE system. People really do not understand what it is about, and mentions the fact that the Nigerian educators of his generation have not gotten out of the old system. However, he hinted that the open university system has been around for over 30 years thereby making it easy for anyone to access formal education without rigidity and that is a milestone for Yoruba-scipedia which began about 15 years ago.

Carrying the baton forward, the Yoruba-scipedia team has introduced the project to many colleges and universities by visiting their campuses to talk to educationists about its values and to ensure that they understand what it is about. Besides the fact that the Yoruba-scipedia is not developing rapidly enough, but slowly, educators need to put more emphasis in order for it to flourish. Being a virtual process and can take in as much as there is, and collaboratively online, all virtual - no limit on size, and resources openly available to everybody.

It is hoped that in the near future other resources, including resources on financial matters, will be added to the encyclopaedia so that universities and the educational system in general can embrace the system.

For the chemist turned lecturer, with OE, education is not for a particular set of people: it is for everybody. Therefore, open educational resources are a useful tool for education, and it needs to be propagated amongst the Nigerian authorities as well as the people at large. Dr. Julius inferred that the next project on the agenda is an illustrated dictionary in Yorùbá language that will attract more people to want to learn.

In similitude to Prof. Jane-Frances' opinion on the issue of setbacks, Dr. Julius averred that the problems facing the sustainability of OE in Nigeria has a political undertone. Unavailability of electricity is a key problem hindering sustainability and the growth of science and technology in Nigeria in order to progress, the frequent, incessant electricity outbreaks and outright blackout limits the virtual experience of citizens. Dr. Julius also stated that the general state of the country in terms of lack of internet connectivity is a big drawback, as many Nigerians are not connected to the internet.

Another limitation to the virtual experience is the level of computer literacy among the people. Only few own a computer and when they do have it there is no electricity to power it. Aside the above listed drawbacks to the educational system in the country, the biggest single problem in the educational system is the rigidity to accept change. Most of the educators were trained in the old system, therefore they see education as an entitlement for the elite, not something that should be thrown open to everybody so this lack of ability to change is still very prevalent in many universities.

In regards to the maintenance and sustenance of the Yoruba-scipedia project, funds are sourced from sales of printed materials as well as donation from supporters and contribution from the association. The Lagos State government has been approached and they promised that soon all schools in Lagos will commence education in the Yoruba language; however, to get funding from them has been a major difficulty.

That said, the association has initiated the process to apply for international grants to sustain the Yoruba-scipedia, nevertheless there is dire need for sponsorship and collaboration with other stakeholders because the project needs to be expanded and improved more frequently so that other materials can go in.

To further develop the education system and make education accessible to all, Dr. Julius is of the opinion that there is need for the translation of the world's knowledge to Nigerian languages, though it is a lot to ask from any institution or individual. On the other hand, localization of resources is paramount in the development of OE in a multi-lingual country like Nigeria, given that most Nigerians (about 80 percent) do not speak fluent English. Most people speak colloquial English and about 10 percent may be able to speak in Pidgin-English. Therefore, that is another limitation in Education and native language education is the only path forward.

5 CONCLUSION

According to both interviewees, the major challenges on the sustenance and maintenance of OER initiative in Nigeria include but are not limited to sluggish interference on the path of government, inadequate funding, and lack of constant electricity power supply, low level of internet connectivity / bandwidth, technophobia and rigidity of the school curriculum.

Consequently, for change to ensue, the solutions demand work, but are achievable: orientation, re-orientation, and education of the Nigerian institutions to accept the trend and make a paradigm shift to the education system. Correspondingly, students need to familiarize themselves with the use of educational resources that are available in the world, as well as keep them abreast of the new developments in Information Communication Technology. Knowledge of ICT should be embedded into the school curriculum at the early years; expensive hardcopy books should be replaced with free and open digital versions and the digital system that allows the synchronization of both asynchronous and synchronous learning approaches should be adopted. But be that as it may, the bulk lies on the table of the government; the education expenditure needs to increase to cater for the implementation of digital education, school renovation and adjustment of the educational system to meet modern times.

As revealed in the foregoing, it is crystal clear that Nigeria is yet to fulfill the UNESCO OER Recommendation; most of the efforts towards the achievement of the recommendation are undertaken by individuals and civil societies. For instance, the likes of Yobamoodua Cultural Heritage and the developers of the Yoruba-scipedia project are playing the role of the messiah through capacity building, awareness creation, developing, translating and distribution of OER in the Yorùbá indigenous language on their own without government grant or support.

Names like Prof. Jane-Frances of the National Open University of Nigeria and the [Nigeria University Commission](#) are also making sure that the second objective of Developing Supportive Policy sees the light of day by leading in the fight for the implementation of an Open Education policy in Nigeria. Their regular teacher professional development programme, dialogue with the government and agitation for an open educational system is getting wide acceptance and gradually getting the right attention.

6 REFLECTION

During the course of data collection for data for the OER World Map, I stumbled on some open but not free sites. The user is required to pay some licensing fee to reuse the content, likewise some sites have the All Rights Reserved limitations, though their content is free to use. It is possible that there are more resources available in the Nigerian sphere that are yet to be added to the map, however the limitation to access them lies on the search queries. Therefore, more resources could be added to the 53 on the map in future. Between, this report on the milestone of OER in Nigeria is highly recommended for anyone who intends to take a sneak peek at the OER landscape and OE milestone in Nigeria.

Above all, I think the OER World Map is a very vital aggregator for anyone involved in Open Education, together with the fact that it enables the sharing of activities surrounding OER across the world, and the crowd sourcing approach which allows anyone to contribute and have access to the World Map, free-of-charge makes it a wonderful tool.

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